

THE UTILIZATION OF OIL FOR HEALING IN AFRICAN CONTEXT: A SUBSTITUTE FOR OLIVE OIL AMONG THE BASSA PEOPLE OF KOGI STATE

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Abstract

The use of African oil for healing seems to be hidden to some, and for those who understand it, they only apply the knowledge, particularly by seeing olive oil to be the only oil for healing and anointing. This has placed olive oil produced by the Middle Easterners and other parts of the world on a higher level than some African oils. And it is even sad to note that most of the olive oils have been adulterated. Some seem to add groundnut oil into containers and other related oils and place high prices on them. It's worse to note that most African preachers and Christians have been mentally and spiritually colonised by the thinking that without olive oil, no healing, no power or anointing. This paper looks into other God given oils available for healing, the power of anointing to help people out of certain perplexing problems. These oils also need prayers of faith, just as it is with the olive oil. These oils are palm oil, kernel oil, groundnut oil, shea butter (manebe molo), which looks like vaseline. This paper relies on a descriptive, analytical, philosophical, and sociological approach.

Key Words: Utilisation, Oil, Healing, Africa, Bassa People

Introduction

Olive oil is mostly in the Middle East, particularly in Israel. It is often used for many other purposes. According to research, it was mostly farmed around the Mount of Gethsamane, which is popularly known as Mountain Olive, simple because on the slope olive, simply because olive trees were being produced. They often squeeze or press out the oil into containers for private and commercial usage. The oil can be edible, used for light, healing, baking and lots more. The

challenge in the use of olive oil is alarming as many including Africans think, healing cannot be done without olive oil, denying the efficacy of other Africa available oils. It is obvious that Africans have substitutes for olive oil. Some have gone too extreme to assume that if not olive oil, healing cannot take place effectively. In Bassa local government Area, there are palm oil (red oil), palm kernel (in Bassa = *menebe mi shiwe*), in Igala (*Okwume*), (*menebe mololo*) a fruit that is edible and contains vitamin which seeds can be heated under sun and melted after several days for consumption in a way of eating, robbing on bruises and lots more.

Oils aside, olive oil among the Bassa people is efficacious as they have been tested and proven good both for consumption and healing. It naturally softens the stomach. Palm oil (red oil) in a small quantity of a peak milk container can be warmed on fire and taken against fever and neutralises even poison in one's stomach.

Clarification of Terms

Terms like oil, healing, and substitute will be clarified for further clarification purposes

- Oil: “a smooth, thick liquid that is made from plants or animals and is used in cooking; olive oil, vegetable oils. It is also a smooth, thick liquid that is made from plants, minerals, etc and is used on the skin or hair (Hornby 811)
- Healing: the process of becoming or making somebody or something healthy again, the process of getting better after an emotional shock (550-551).
- Substitute: a person or thing that you use or have instead of the one you normally use or have; a player who replaces another player in a sports game. Verb = to take the place of somebody or something else (1196).

Olive Oil in the Biblical World

The Hebrew word for oil is (*Shemen* and in the Greek it is *elaion*), in the Bible almost always olive oil, perhaps the only exception being Esther 2:12, where it is oil of myrrh. Research has it that the “olives” were beaten according to (Lev. 24:2), and other times trodden upon (Mic. 6:15), but in a most general way it was “crushed) in a mill designed for that purpose. In some situations, a very big stone was put upon all for the purpose of pressing to have the oil pressed out into containers.

Merrill explained the usage of olive oil in biblical times when she said:

Olive oil was not only a prime article of food, the bread being dipped in it, but it was also used for cooking, for anointing, and for lighting. Oil was one of the principal ingredients in making soap (Jer. 2 22).

Anointing with oil was for three diverse purposes: wounded animals were anointed for the soothing and corrective effects of the oil (Ps. 23:5);

People anointed themselves with oil for its cosmetic value (Ps. 104:15); but notably men were anointed as an official inauguration into high office. Priests (Exod. 24:41; 29:7),

Prophets, and kings (I Kings 19:15) were anointed and were called “messiah” i.e., “anointed ones” (Lev. 4:3,5,16; I Sam. 2:10; I Chron. 16:22).

Anointing the head of a guest with oil was a mark of high courtesy (Luke 7:46). Oil is also used as a symbol for the Holy Spirit. Our Lord’s Messiahship was not bestowed with the use of Literal oil, but was evidenced when the Holy Spirit came down upon Him in the form of a dove at His baptism (Luke 3:22, etc).

Oil was also the prime source of light in the dwelling and in the tabernacle. It was contained in little clay vessels so arranged that a wick lying in the oil was supported at one end, where the oil burned and furnished just about “one candle power” of light (603)

Each time oil is mentioned in the scripture, it often refers to olive oil, which some directly call anointing oil. The significance of oil to man cannot be overemphasised as it can cure several illnesses and anoint either individuals or groups set for service. However significant olive oil was and is, it is still interesting to note that oil made from palm kernel called (*Aledi*), and oil squeezed from groundnut, oil gotten from some available fruits in Africa and many more are also useful to play the role olive oil plays that is either for anointing, for robbing bruises, and to be used for cooking and other known usages. On the use of olive, Karren et al. explained that:

Usually the product of olive trees, oil was an essential part of everyday life in Biblical times (2 Kings 18:32; Matt. 25:3).it was used in trade, religious ceremonies, food preparation, cosmetics, as medicine, and for lamplight. Oil was used in the conservation of priests and kings. Among other things, oil symbolises joy (Isa.. 61:3, Ps. 45:7), 167-169).

The above quotation proves that the oil discussed in the Bible, in most cases, has to do with olive oil, which is a product of the olive tree. This was often farmed in

the Middle East, and even on the slope of the mountain, it was planted, and it became known as mountain olive because on that slope, they press the fruit to squeeze out the oil into containers. Jesus often goes there for prayers (Matthew 26:36). The Gestsemane means “oil press”, the place for squeezing oil from olives (see note on Mark 14:32).

In describing the olive tree, Karren et al further explained that: the tree does not grow fast but slowly, a crooked tree and has a greater value in biblical times (Deut. 6:11; Rom. 11:17). It is often cultivated and its height is about twenty feet. It can live for hundreds of years. It is a multi-purpose in usage. The tree symbolises fruitfulness, and the branch of the olive tree is a symbol of peace (170).

Kings, priests, prophets and others were anointed with this oil for power, and identification with God’s sacredness and presence before, during service.

African Countries

Africa is one of the seven continents in the world, which are namely: Asia, Africa, North America, South America, Antarctica, Europe and Australia. A continent is one of Earth’s seven main divisions of land. They often begin with the largest to the smallest, but this research concerns the Bassa-speaking people of Nigeria, on the African continent.

The African continent has 58 Countries, and they are as follows:

Nigeria	Algeria	Mali
Ethopia	Moroco	Burkina Faso
Egypt	Angola	Malawi
Democratic Republic of Tanzania	Ghana	Zambia
	Mozambique	Chad
South Africa	Madagascar	Somalia
Kenya	Cote d'Ivoire	Senegal
Uganda	Cameroon	Zimbabwe
Sudan	Niger	Guinea
Rwanda	Liberia	Eswatino
Benin	Mauritania	Djibouti
Burundi	Eritrea	Reunion

Tunisia	Gambia	Comoros
South Sudan	Botswana	Cabo Verde
Togo	Namibia	Western SaharaMayotte
Sierra Leone	Gabon	São Tomé and Príncipe
Libya	Lesotho	Seychelles
Congo	Guinea-Bissau	Saint Helena
Central African Republic	Equatorial Guinea	www.worldometers.info
	Mauritius	

Africa has five (5) regions and they are: West Africa, East Africa, South Africa, North Africa, Central Africa (Kome 18)

Edible oil in Africa:

1. Nara oil
2. Mongongo oil
3. Marula oil
4. Egusi oil
5. Akabanga

Edible oils in Nigeria:

1. Olive oil
2. Sesame oil
3. Avocado oil
4. Canola oil
5. Peanut oil

The researcher concentrates on an ethnic group in West Africa. They are called Bassa with a Local Government in Kogi State. Though they are also found in Nassarawa, Abuja, Niger Benue. Their dispersal is never a challenge, as they all understand the various oils that can substitute olive oil for healing, as seen in the Bible world.

Geographically, Bassa Local Government Area is located between latitude 33⁰ degrees north of the equator and longitude 6⁰.30 and 7⁰.5 East of Greenwich Meridian with an area of 233.735, 59km and a population of over 107.001 (Local Government Survey Department). The Local Government has a population density of 5,4466 people per 59km. according to Wabare, “Bassa Local Government Area covers an area of 6,485 square miles. It was bounded on the

North land west by the rivers Benue and Nigeria respectively, on the South by the Southern Nigeria, and Muri province on the East” (10).

Musa explained that:

Bassa Local Government Area is also bounded by Omala Local Government to the east while it shares a boundary with Dekina to the South. In the river Benue and West part is the Niger Benue and West Past is the Niger-Benue wrought. It has a moderate rainfall. The rain generally begins in the Local government Area between the months of March/April and extends to October/November... (26)

The quotation portrays the location and whether periods of the Bassa land in Kogi State. They are mostly farmers and civil servants. They are blessed with fertile land that suits Agricultural activities. They have fish ponds at various locations. The Bassa people are religiously inclined. They are 90% Christian, 19% Africa religionists and 1% Muslims. Bassa kingdom is a booming commercial centre as economic activities can obviously be seen and enjoyed.

Types of oils among the Bassa people

There are various oil that are common among the Bassa people that serve several purposes. Oils are vital among Bassa people as all the available ones can be used for healings and at the same time are edible. The following therefore are the oils produced for healings and are edible:

- i. Palm oil (*Bassa-umuzhimi*)
- ii. Palm karnel oil extraction (*manebe mi shiwe*)
- iii. Groundnut oil (*manebe mu gwezhe*)
- iv. Python’s oil (*manebe mu uhwa ‘wutu*)
- v. Shear butter (*manebe mololo*)
- vi. Coconut oil (*manebe mu utahuba*) cures breast cancer

The use of oils for healing among Bassa people: This African ethnic group has wider knowledge on the use of oils, both edible and healing. The oils are often famous except for the python oils and the Turkey oils.

They are as follows:

- **Palm Oil:** Palm oil is made from the ripened red kernel. After being removed from the ripped red kernel, after being removed from its stock, it has been processed into oil. Oil, according to an oral source, is medicinal to humans.
- i. Ruwo says: oil softens one's tummy, and helps in quick digestion, which also helps in passing a flexible stool (interview)

- ii. It helps to neutralise poison. When unknowingly one takes in poison and it is quickly discovered, oil is forced into the victim by using a teaspoon as it goes into neutralise the poison. The victim or patient could vomit to get relief (interview)
- iii. Zogbogu observed that: oil, when turned into a small container and warmed on fire and taken in a small quantity, could cure malaria fever. In a situation where it doesn't give a positive result, the patient could visit the hospital for a proper test and diagnosis (interview)
- iv. According to Zuma, an elderly woman, oil helps in curing skin diseases like heat-related afflictions that often cause body itching. Oil is applied sometimes alone so it cools one's body and allows the patient to sleep out. This skin affection is called (*upa*) in Bassa. The researcher suffered from this *upa* early 2023 (January-February), until he was advised to apply oil with kerosene or alum.
- v. Oil can also be used to heal a fresh or a thorn-pierced leg, nail puncture of someone's leg after removing the piece of iron, nail, broken bottle, thorn, oil is applied and heated to a coated fire, as the heat and oil penetrate, it cures or heals the wound from the inside to the outer part. In physical healing, Adamo mentioned oil as one of the means used to cure smallpox when he said:

Prophet Adewole recommends Palm 84 to be read ten times over with the holy name Alojah Alojah Alojah to be pronounced 21 times or a mixture of fried oil, potash, shear butter, with the reading of Psalm 84 into it. The oil is for rubbing the body and the water for bathing... for convulsion, read Psalm 1 over water for drinking and bathing and pronounce the holy name Hela Hola 84 times on the head of the sick person. Or mix oil, dry gin or brandy with potash, and blue alum, and read Psalm 1 with the holy name above for drinking and rubbing on the body (64, 65).

The quotation above points to prayers, the bible and natural elements like oil to perfect healing. It implies that oil, not olive oil, does the healing, as one does not remain mentally and spiritually colonised. They develop faith for healing. They are cultural, so some available African cultural materials should be used, so they won't remain in the bondage of olive oil before healing. In promoting African cultural identity and means of healing, Adamo explained that:

... African mode of interpretation “seeks to acquire and celebrate their God-giving identity by delving

into their indigenous resources and rejecting the superintending tendencies of Western intellectual tradition... they address issues closer home to their own people. What they did was that they “learnt and borrowed ideas and techniques from external resources but reshaped them, often added their own indigenous texture, to meet their local needs. God is not a one-way track God. His mode of revelation to the world cannot be limited... (2)

Adamo observed that African indigenous resources are God’s gifts that should be recognised and celebrated. It implies that the means of healing can be contextualised to bring Africans closer to what is available within them. Oil, therefore, is one of the healing elements that is capable of healing both some physical and spiritual diseases.

Palm Kernal Oil Extraction (*manebe mishiwe*)

This kernel is the inner part of palm oil removed, broken from one of the nuts. It can be dried and fried. The kernel during frying gradually melts and turns liquid to give kernel oil. It is dark in nature and has a special aroma that can be perceived from a distance. Palm kernel oil has many uses to humans. *en.m.wikipedia.org* explained that:

Palm kernel oil is an edible plant oil derived from the kernel of the oil palm tree, *Elaeis guinensis*. It is related to the other two edible oils: palm oil, extracted from the fruit pulp of the oil palm, and coconut oil, extracted from the kernel of the coconut. Palm kernel oil, palm oil, and coconut. Palm kernel oil, palm oil, and coconut oil are three of the few highly saturated vegetable fat; these oils give the name to the 16-carbon saturated fatty acid Palmitic that they contain. Palm kernel oil, which is semi-solid at room temperature, is more saturated than palm oil and comparable to coconut oil. Aghalino (19-33).

It is edible in many areas. The quotation above explained that “kernel oil is an edible plant oil... it is taken or extracted from the pulp of the oil palm. When kept in a cool environment, it becomes stive, but when heated, it melts. It is mostly found or recognised in “West African and central African countries”. Research has it that “European merchants trading with West Africa occasionally purchased palm oil for use in Europe, but palm kernel oil remained rare outside West Africa”

Palm kernel oil is high in lauric acid, which has been shown to raise blood cholesterol levels, both as LDLC (cholesterol contained in high-density lipoprotein)... palm kernel oil is commonly used in commercial cooking because it is lower in cost than other oils. It remains stable at high cooking temperatures.

The oil can be stored longer than other vegetable oils Poku (3). Other defined uses of kernel oil are:

- i. It is used in cooking rice, yams, potatoes, Potages, plaiting of hair, robbing as cream and smoothing the body-Ruwo (Interview).
- ii. Kernel oil is used to cure ear-related diseases by applying a small quantity, supporting the oil with a cotton ball, so that the ear is cleansed. Spiritual problems can still be cured.
- iii. It cools the body when faced with the heat of the body. So, to a child's body, hotness. Praying on the oil as it is with the olive oil, cures spiritually related issues among Africans.
- iv. It substitutes red oil when taking a particular medicine that forbids consuming palm oil, this could be for several months or weeks
- v. According to Zuma, during an interview, kernel oil is used in the preparation of some special medicine, like children's diseases, which is called *jedijedi* in Yoruba. It fights some germs and heals bruises when applied to the physical body and taken in to stool out for freedom.

Groundnut oil (*manebe me ugwezhe*)

It is a kind of oil extracted from groundnuts when broken and pressed or grinned. It is smooth and has a good taste and aroma. The oil has the following as uses:

- i. Helps speed up metabolism. In fact, according to research, those who eat peanut oil or groundnut oil like healthier and experience more weight loss. Groundnuts are high in protein, fat, several vitamins and minerals. According to studies, groundnuts lower the risk of heart diseases and may also help with weight loss. Groundnuts are rich in fat, with mono and polyunsaturated fatty acids.
- ii. It is a good source of plant-based proteins and is low in carbohydrates. This makes them a healthy dietary option for diabetes.
- iii. Groundnut or peanut oil keeps Blood pressure under control. Research shows that groundnuts lower blood pressure and reduce the load on the cardiovascular system.
- iv. It prevents Arthritis as it has high anti-inflammatory characteristics. This is a cooking to keep arthritis at bay. It also helps to strengthen. Cold-pressed oil helps relieve joint pain by reducing inflammation in the joints.
- v. It soothes and energises one, and can help relieve muscle pain. When applied regularly, this provides excellent comfort for painful muscles and joints. It is good is nurturing of body's skin. The oil is used in aromatherapy.
- vi. Groundnut oil serves as an anti-ageing. The peanut oil slows down the ageing speed and is high in vitamin E. The oil helps in diminishing

signs of ageing such as dark spots, fine lines, wrinkles, uneven skin, and pigmentation (Evros, Kvassiliou n.p).

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19558671/>.

The researcher's intention for this research is to enlighten the readers on various oils that can be used to do the miracle olive oil does in both the Middle East, Europe, the West and even in the African continent. Groundnut oil can be substituted for olive oil to prevent various diseases among the Bassa people and the entire African.

Python oil

This oil is extracted from a dead python, that is, a wild snake. Python oil is a multi-purpose oil with the efficacy of healing several cases in the human body. Local, when a python is killed and roasted, the cutting of the Tommy shows the oil and often a container is set to pour out the oil (Ndazhaga Interview). The oil can be cooked as in heated and can be stored for a long period of time. It does the following:

- i. Cures joint pain; this is by gently robbing the affected areas
- ii. Python oil cures rheumatic pain
- iii. Toothache
- iv. Eye sight
- v. It helps to cure stretch marks
- vi. Arthritis

It implies that dislocations can be cured via Python oil as it can be applied on a daily basis on the patient. The oil penetrates down to the marrow and causes the joining of the bones. A religious person is therefore expected to pray a prayer of faith for quick healing. The people develop strong faith for healing (Genegu Interview). Most of the healings are done through application to the affected parts. And it is necessary for the entire body like the case of stretch marks.

This oil, when used or applied for any kind of expected healing, it must always go along with prayers of faith, reading Psalms 20 & 40 into this oils with the holy name Eli Safatan (62 time) (Adamo 25). Africans are blessed with several therapeutic elements and results. All of these oils mentioned are mostly python oil mostly is for physical application and should go along with Bible passage application and should go along with Bible passage that has to do with healing. Example: Psalms 1, 2, 3, 6, 20, and 40 are for the healing of various diseases, which oils can cure (Adamo, 24, 25).

Share Butter (*Manebe mololo*)

This oil is an extraction from a kind of fruit that is taken from a particular tree called *Uyigo* in Bassa. The fruit contains vitamin C. The seed is round in nature.

After the Green part is eaten, the seeds are stored under sun for a period of two (2) weeks or more, then they are broken out of it sheld and the inner seed, which is the main oil-producing part, is heated in a very sealed container where it will gradually melt and turn to real oil. The oil has a taste and draws, thick, whitish in nature, and contains elements of gum in it. This oil cures and does the following: dislocation or joint pains can be eaten to soften one's stomach, can be used to rob a newborn child against (*jedijedi*), which affects the physical body of a baby. This oil can be rubbed on any affected place. It is often used to cure other diseases or ailments on the human body (Isaac Interview). It smoothens the body. The use of this among the Bassa people cannot be overemphasised as they have served as healing elements in many centuries and even more today.

Chronic illness can be cured with the use of oils and prayers of faith in line with reading the scriptures for more effective results. As Africans, there are several substitutes for the Eurocentric-produced drugs and other means of healing. This, Adamo has to say:

Treatment for chronic illness: fill a new pot with water and read Psalms 21 twenty times and light 12 candles around the pot, call the holy names Dabola, Elijah and use the water for bathing and drinking. One can also mix coconut oil, shea butter, one egg and read Psalms 21 and the holy names above for drinking and rubbing on the body. Offer a prayer for purification. For convulsion, read Psalm 1 over water for drinking and bathing. Hola 84 times on the head of the sick person, or mix oil, dry gin or brandy with potash and blue alum, and read Psalm 1 with the holy name above for drinking and rubbing on the body. Bolarinwa also believes that these Psalms are potent for curing toothache, headache and backache. For a toothache, these psalms must be read into lukewarm water, and the patient should rinse his mouth with it until the tumbler is empty. The process can be repeated from time to time (65).

The author projects the African use of the Bible for curing various types of illness and other application methods. The bible, therefore, is a multi-purpose manual for African Christians so they won't be stranded when facing complicated health challenges. The Bible has both the spiritual power, the natural elements, and a method of application to be free from the bondage of illness.

The Bassa people are talented in the usage of herbs for curing various kinds of illness, but this paper focuses on oils as a substitute for olive oil in the Bible, which should be given more attention in order to portray their potencies and

values in society. This way, African Christians would not be slaves to olive oil as there are substitutes.

Recommendations

The researcher recommends that Africans, particularly the Bassa Pastors, prayer warriors and herbalists who serve as agents and instruments of healing, should give recognition to African gifted Oils, so they would be able to exploit in healing activities within and outside their domain.

Medical personnel should also value African Oils for the cure of some ailments, as not all ailments should require foreign oils for treatment.

Edible oils, as discussed earlier by the researcher, should be used as food, not all should be spiritualized.

Praying and developing faith in God on African gifted Oils for healing will always give mitigants to so many persisting ailments as God would want to use them.

In applying African gifted Oils, strictly follow the guides given to you for effective results

Conclusion

The researchers' aim in this paper is to call the attention of the Bassa people and other Africans who are more into healing activities via herbs and olive oil, to the other God given oils around them. The researcher, therefore, looks into palm oil, palm kernel oil, groundnut oil, python oil, and others as vital and hence can substitute olive oil to cure the sick stomach ache, dislocation, joint pains, fever, jaundice and other illnesses. In view of this, Africans should value and put into practice what is in their hands for effective healing in society. In view of this, Africans should value and put into practice what is in their hands for effective healing in society. And in using other available oils, it will be more efficacious when prayers and faith development is put into action or demonstrated. Studying passages of the bible that are related to a particular illness and applying the organised prayers there is a necessity.

Works Cited

- Adamo, D.T. *Explorations in Africans Biblical Studies*. Benin City: Justice Jeco Press & Publishers Ltd, 2005.
- Hornby, A.S. *Oxford advanced Learner's Dictionary*. York: Oxford University Press, 2000
- Karen. D. et al. *The Students Bible Dictionary*. Barbour: Holman Bible Publishers. 2000.
- Kome, U.M. *New Standard Current Affairs*. Port-Harcourt: Kume Publication Ventures, n.d.
- Merrill, Tenney C. (G.ed). *The Zondervan Pictorial Bible Dictionary*. Michigan: Zondervan Publishing House, 1967.
- Wabare, Paul. *The Bassa Speaking People of Nigeria*. Ahmadu Bello University Press, Ltd, 1993.

Table of Oral Sources

S/N	Name	Designation	Religion	Age	Place of Interview	Date of Interview
1.	Ruwo E.Musa	Business/Farming	Christianity	C.40Years	Anyigba	22/05/2025
2.	Zogbogu DJoel	Student/Herbalist /Hunter	Christianity	C 21Years	Gagba	22/05/2025
3.	Zuma John	Business/Farming	Christianity	C.73Years	Edenye	24/05/2025
4.	Ndazhaga Daudu	Farming/Herbalist	Traditionalist	C.75Years	Kporo	01/06/2025
5.	Genegu Ndazhaga	Pastoral Ministry	Christianity	C.37Years	Etikpol	03/06/2025
6.	Isaac E. Gwatana	Pastor/Herbalist	Christianity	C. 37Years	Ubutu	05/06/2025